

Contribution of Broadcast Media Campaigns in Law Enforcement on Crime Prevention in Rwanda: A Case of Rwanda Broadcasting Agency

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Abstract: This study aimed to examine the contribution of broadcast media campaigns in law enforcement on crime prevention in Rwanda: A case of Rwanda Broadcasting Agency. This research was a mixed research design with both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The study utilized the simple random and purposive sampling technique. To determine the sample size of 92 respondents, Yamane's formula was used. The quantitative data was gathered using structured questionnaire, while qualitative data was gathered using focus group discussion. For quantitative data, study employed both descriptive and inferential statistics. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 26 version) facilitated data analysis, enabling a more understanding of how broadcast media campaign contributes to crime prevention efforts, while thematic analysis was used for qualitative data collected in group discussion conducted to the 19 Law enforcement officers working in the media department and crime prevention division guided by Deputy Director of department at Kimihurura headquarters located in Kigali City, Rwanda. The results showed that the relationship between contribution of broadcast media campaigns in law enforcement and crime prevention was .868** which showed that there was a statistically significant correlation between broadcast media campaigns in law enforcement and crime prevention in Rwanda by RBA. It demonstrated that a statistically significant correlation existed between the role of broadcast media coverage of audio-visual information in law enforcement and crime prevention in Rwanda by RBA. The study concluded that there was a significant relationship between the broadcast media use in law enforcement and crime prevention in Rwanda at RBA. The study recommended that Rwanda broadcasting agency and Law enforcement agency should continue to develop and improve their collaboration in the way of using broadcast media in law enforcement for the purpose of crime prevention in Rwandan society.

Keywords: Broadcasting, Community engagement, Crime prevention, Law enforcement, Radio broadcasting, Rwanda broadcasting agency, Television broadcasting.

I. INTRODUCTION

Broadcast media house and law enforcement partnership is eminent and plays a complementary role in enhancing public safety in what is described to be a complex loop of interdependence. Media and law enforcement institutions symbiose in such a way law enforcement are assisted with media coverage in crime prevention, detection and holding up their image, as the foundation of its news reports, the media consistently receives releases of crime and crash data (Thompson & Miller, 2023). Both local broadcast media channels and law enforcement agencies are social institutions for democratic government. The presence of both broadcast media journalists and law enforcement officers at crime scenes underscores the often tense

but potentially collaborative relationship between the two parties (Jones & Smith, 2021). While journalists aim to report facts to the public, law enforcement seeks to maintain control over the crime scene and manage sensitive information. This dynamic, however, can be transformed into a strategic partnership focused on crime reduction rather than merely reporting (Brown, 2022). By working together through joint media briefings, shared crime prevention campaigns, and coordinated public alerts both parties can contribute to public safety more effectively, thereby reducing the need for frequent media attendance at every crime scene (Thompson & Miller, 2023).

A good crime prevention strategy depends on fostering community trust and influencing public views, both of which are greatly influenced by law enforcement's presence in the broadcast media. When law enforcement officials actively engage with broadcast media, they provide timely information, transparency, and accountability, which can help bridge the gap between police and the community (Goldsmith, 2020). The visibility of law enforcement on trusted media platforms reinforces the credibility of crime prevention messages. Research indicates that when law enforcement officers are seen on respected media outlets, it enhances the audience's trust not only in the officers but also in the media platform itself (Schlesinger & Tumber, 2018). This mutual trust can lead to increased public cooperation, such as reporting crimes or providing tips, which are vital for effective crime prevention (Chermak & Weiss, 2022).

Moreover, the presence of law enforcement in the media helps demystify their work, offering the public insight into their efforts, challenges, and successes. This transparency fosters a sense of security and confidence in law enforcement's ability to manage public safety (Tyler, 2019). As a result, the community is more likely to engage in proactive crime prevention behaviors, such as participating in neighborhood watch programs or following police advice disseminated through media broadcasts. In essence, the synergy between law enforcement's strategic media presence and the community's trust in both the media and law enforcement creates a powerful feedback loop that enhances public cooperation and strengthens crime prevention strategies (Graziano, Schuck, & Martin, 2020).

Choice of broadcast media to be used by law enforcement should be based on media confidence and where the target audience is most active (example Kiss FM, B&B FM, Umwezi radio station for youth generation), considering both private and public broadcasts media preference in delivering information. Crime prevention campaign involves several key steps prior to commencement including establishing clear and measurable objectives for the campaign, ensuring the target audience is reached and communication is impactful. Another media strategy for law enforcement involves use of various types of content tailored for radio or television and as well both, press, audio supported with videos, and public service announcements for successful awareness.

Formerly around the 9th century in different parts of the world, there were no specific individuals tasked with law enforcement, small community residents managed to guarantee their safety using informal means of social control. During middle age fear to commit crime was created using a reprisals system together with street lamps were attached to the outer doors and corners of the house to discourage criminals. Later in the 13th century, a neighborhood watch system was introduced like the watchman system in London, the Chowkidar in Middle East and South Asia and "Irondo ry'Umwuga" translated as professional night patrol in Rwanda. Those volunteers kept watch over a village walking in streets to incapacitate any attempt of night prowlers. From the period of post-colonial Rwanda and pre-Genocide era "Irondo" concept seemed not enough because citizens continued to suffer insecurity resulting in 1994 genocide against TUTSI as a consequence of bad ruling governance (Barhuta, 2017).

Prior to the RPF assuming military rule over the entirety of Rwanda in July 1994, a noticeable Security Sector Reforms (SSRs) including formation of Rwanda National Police (RNP) in the year 2000 from perfunctory groups: Gendarmerie Nationale, Communal Police and the Judicial police inspectors (RNP, 2015). It was until 09th April 2018, the Government of Rwanda thought it is wiser to have two hand in hand law enforcement institutions created Rwanda Investigation Bureau (RIB) mandated to perform career criminal investigation formerly under RNP responsibility. These two law enforcement agencies are found in strong partnership with the public in fighting crimes. Both RNP and RIB as a proactive force strengthened the community policing concept that enables officers and civilians to share critical information that is used to overcome crime in Rwandan society.

In the changing nature of community and in shifting characteristics of crime and violence during the last quarter of a century, traditional policing which was based on stopping crime primarily through harsh punishment so that members of the community could fear to engage in criminality. In turn, law enforcement found that traditional policing worked in the past is not an effective sense of safety, security has not been achieved while police officers work day-night arresting through.

Over the years, many law enforcement agencies around the globe innovated a concept of Community policing, a police-public partnership to build a strong bond of ownership, confidence and trust (Thompson & Miller, 2023).

At this time, law enforcement officers are no longer bureaucratic waiting for intervention at crime scenes after crimes have been committed. This isolation hampers crime-fighting efforts since police are limited to pertinent information from citizens that could help solve or deter crime. Through community policing, information sharing between community members and police will be forthcoming as long as law enforcement institutions establish a relationship of trust with the community they serve. Working professionally and transparently raises public trust and legitimacy during law enforcer interactions. Effective policing is nearly difficult when there is a lack of confidence between the police and the public because knowledge exchanged becomes hearsay. However, the trust of the citizens existing in the police should reflect the trust of the police in citizens vice-versa. Therefore, Police-public working together requires mutual trust, respect and support (Schaap, 2018).

Since establishment of Rwanda media commission (RMC) in 2013, RNP widen its collaboration with RMC member journalists associated in different radios and TV stations including Radio Rwanda, Radio 1, Flash FM, KT radio, Contact FM, Isango Star FM, RTV, TV10 Rwanda, TV1 Rwanda, Loyal TV, Flash TV, and BTN Rwanda to name just few clarifies the commitment RNP put forward in documenting awareness messages. In addition, when the Rwanda investigation bureau was created in 2018 to detect and investigate crimes, crime prevention is among the main responsibilities shared with Rwanda national police to create safe working environment. However, there are remaining issues to address including limited amount of awareness campaigns, few multichannel communications used, and shortage trained public relation officers thwarting the willingness of the public to share information as people are not yet aware for instance who and what telephone number to call on suspicious activity in the surrounding. The study conducted in 2019 with Rwanda Governance Board showed that RIB is not well-known hundred percent by the people while it is an institution mandated for collaborating with citizens to combat crimes.

The researcher was motivated with this study to contribute to the body of knowledge of crime prevention in regard to law enforcement should utilize radio and television means of communication channels to overcome escalating crimes. Rwanda population is increasing and not only developing in whole sectors, besides to achieve security and safe working environment free from corruption, burglary, rape, battery, murder, fraud, drug abuse and other white-collar crimes ought to be mitigated. Advancement of technology and globalization effect caused crimes evolving and growing exponentially. Law enforcement is unable to deploy in every crime hotspot. Therefore, it is in this regard collaboration with community residents who know the region is beneficial. Use of broadcasts media by law enforcement provides a durable and affordable means of crime prevention strategy. It is in context that media play a positive role in their ability to affect public perception of crime as a social phenomenon.

The broadcast media continually and methodically influences people's way of thinking and creating patterns of behavior (Rotter 2021). Certainly, they do have an impact on education given that the popular media are often called the "informal public teacher" through a program of judging deviants community members for example a program that uses real-life stories or case studies to show how individuals who committed crimes underestimated the risks and faced severe consequences. This approach can deter others by emphasizing that crime does not pay, highlighting stories showing how criminal records limit job opportunities, access to financial services, and social mobility, making the costs of crime outweigh any perceived benefits.

Long-term exposure to media, especially TV screens, shapes viewers' views of reality. According to Potter (2014), heavy viewers who watch crime-related information frequently come to believe that the world is more dangerous than it actually is. Television and video games are not the only factors affecting people's view of the real world what is called counterproductive effect in which media based anticrime campaigns that have effects opposite to the campaign goal of crime reduction. Every law enforcement agency needs fostering a viable media-relation through regular meetings to discuss issues of mutual interest and responsibility of local media themselves in ensuring security and crime prevention as implied in the code of ethics. Depending on the crime wave, law enforcement agencies will take a quick look at recognizing radio and TV broadcasting before any other platforms to share warning notice, awareness about new evolved crimes such as cybercrimes and timely crime reporting. Additionally, law enforcement should continuously train Public Information Officers (PIOs) responsible for handling news media inquiries. The PIOs ought to be qualified in written and oral communication, have organization skills and be cognizant of the importance of collaborating with media. Professional media officers are expected to exploit media tools for crime intelligence gathering (Martin & Scassa, 2017).

There are many instances where law enforcement agencies rely on information circulating in the media in support of intelligence assessments and investigations, this has generated a particular interest for crime prevention policy making. Broadcast media often report on various criminal incidents that, when analyzed collectively, can reveal broader patterns and emerging threats. Crime intelligence departments can use media reports as data points to map crime hotspots, identify new crime trends, or detect changes in criminal behavior. This information complements official crime data and enhances predictive policing efforts (Hardyns & Rummens, 2018). News coverage often captures on-the-ground details, eyewitness accounts, and context that might not be immediately available to law enforcement.

This can be crucial during rapidly unfolding events, such as riots, terror attacks, or natural disasters, where intelligence from media reports helps law enforcement adjust their strategies accordingly (Brown, 2018). There is thus every reason law enforcers become aware of utilizing broadcast media to predict crime before it actually happens using data obtained from various media programs. This can be achieved through analyzing available crime patterns and trends as repetitive patterns have been found in crime occurrence. This pattern can be identified through the analysis of various factors such as the type of crime being committed, the time they happen, location, modus operandi used, and the computer algorithms can exploit even common characteristics shown by affected victims and this fact. Although not all crimes are predicted in this way, once a prediction is made aids law enforcement resources allocation and can increase patrolling hotspot at the appropriate time knowing where and when the crimes are supposed to occur. This presence may then discourage eventual felons of doing prohibited activities, reducing in this way the crime occurrence rate.

Broadcast media played a crucial role in promoting this philosophy, with public relation departments using, radio, and TV to highlight their community engagement efforts. Campaigns such as "McGruff the Crime Dog" used television to educate children and families about crime prevention. These campaigns aimed to involve the community in safety efforts and foster a sense of shared responsibility for crime reduction. Studies have shown that public awareness campaigns can effectively reduce crime rates (McLaughlin, 2023).

For instance, Braga, *et al.*, (2012) conducted an analysis of burglary prevention campaigns and found that areas with active media campaigns experienced a significant reduction in burglary incidents. These campaigns often included practical tips on securing homes and identifying suspicious activities. The impact of anti-drug media campaigns in urban settings. Their findings indicated that such campaigns, which included a mix of television advertisement, social media posts, and community outreach programs, led to increased public awareness about the risks of drug use and a subsequent decrease in drug-related crimes (Braga, *et al.*, 2012).

The introduction of McGruff the Crime Dog in the 1980s, marked a significant media campaign aimed at educating children about safety and crime prevention. This campaign used television commercials, school programs, and community events to promote safety tips and foster a sense of responsibility among young people. Over two decades have passed since the start of the McGruff campaign. Two extensive assessments have been completed. The first was carried out between 1979 and 1981, and O'Keefe and Mendelsohn published the findings. A nationwide poll of 1,200 adults from all around the US was conducted for this study.

The findings indicated that while around half of the participants had seen the campaign announcements, just 3% of them could recall the commercial without interviewers' assistance. In 1992, the same research team carried out a follow-up assessment. In this instance, a national sample of individuals was questioned in addition to members of the media and law enforcement. According to this survey, 80% of participants said they had seen the notifications, and both law enforcement and the media reported similar favorable outcomes. The "Take a Bite Out of Crime" campaign, according to Lab, generally assists people who are already interested in crime prevention issues and those who are generally the least likely to commit crimes to change their attitudes.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study employed mixed method research design with both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The quantitative and qualitative data sets were analyzed independently using appropriate methods. For the most part, a quantitative component was used to get the numerical data that were examined statistically. These data provided measurable evidence of the effectiveness and reach of broadcasting media campaigns and their contribution on crime prevention efforts. Interview guide for focus group discussions with law enforcement officers at a convenient time and ensure participants have varying levels of experience with media use provide a more elaborate understanding of the phenomenon of interest.

The area of study was Gasabo district in Kigali city targeting a headquarters of Rwanda Broadcasting Agency. Presence of public relation and crime prevention division officers, their expertise provided valuable insights into the strategies and effectiveness of radio and TV use for public outreach and crime prevention campaigns. Public relation department and the crime prevention division work together to assess how various broadcast media campaign affect the crime rate, they also set common objectives such as lowering particular crime types and monitoring media coverage.

The population and categories

Category of respondents	Populations
Law enforcement officers	24
Media journalist/presenters (RBA)	96
Total	120

Source: RBA, (2025)

A sample size, as defined by Creswell, (2014), is a subset of the population from which conclusions can be drawn about the full population. A Yamane's formula was used to calculate the sample size as follow:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} = \frac{120}{1+120(0.05)^2} = \frac{120}{1.3} = 92.3 \approx 92$$

Where:

n: is a sample size, **N:** study population, **e:** is a margin error

A sample of ninety-two (92) respondents were chosen for this investigation.

Sample size determination

Category of respondents	Study Population	Sample size
Law enforcement officers	24	19
Media journalist/presenters (RBA)	96	73
Total	120	92

Source: RBA, (2025)

In this study, simple random and purposive sampling technique were utilized to ensure a comprehensive and insightful examination of broadcast media campaign in law enforcement for crime prevention. Purposive sampling which was used for law enforcement officers selection of sample size based on their departmental roles specifically, the public relations department and the crime prevention division. Simple random sampling which was also used on media journalists' selection of sample.

The data was collected using questionnaire and Focus Group Discussion(FGD). These methods were chosen to capture both quantitative and qualitative data. Questionnaire was administered to participants, designed to gather quantitative data about their exposure to crime prevention messages broadcasted on media platforms like radio and television. The focus group discussion, research collected the data by transcription of the audio recording, coding the text to identify key themes and recurring ideas, categorizing responses based on the asked questions.

The researcher used the descriptive statistics to summarize the demographic data of participants and key variables. This included frequencies, means, standard deviations, and percentages to describe the level of media exposure and community engagement. Inferential Statistics were used to explore relationships variables. The study used the SPSS (version 26). For qualitative analysis, the thematic analysis was applied by Converting the audio recording of the discussion into written text, ensuring accuracy and capturing non-verbal cues where possible.

III. RESULTS

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

In order to establish a baseline statistic for the research findings, the researcher looked into the demographic traits of the respondents that were significant to them. Age, gender, education, and job experience were the demographic factors. The following table displayed the results:

Age Group of Respondents

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	18-29	11	12.0
	30-44	48	52.2
	45-60	27	29.3
	Above 60	6	6.5
	Total	92	100.0

Source: RBA, (2025)

This table presents the age group of Respondents. The researcher was interested in the respondents' age group distribution. Out of 92 respondents, 12.0% were in the range of 18-29 years, the 52.2% were in the range of 30-44 years, 29.3% were in the range of 45-60 years, and 6.5% were in the range of above 60 years.

Gender of Respondents

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Male	57	62.0
	Female	35	38.0
	Total	92	100.0

Source: RBA, (2025)

The respondents' gender breakdown is seen in above table. The gender distribution of the respondents piqued the researcher's interest. Men made up 62.0% of the 92 responders, while women made up 38.0%.

Educational Level of Respondents

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Vocational training	44	47.8
	University or Higher	48	52.2
	Total	92	100.0

Source: Primary data, (2025)

Above table presents education level distribution of respondents. The researcher was interested in the respondents' education levels. Out of 92 respondents, 47.8% held a vocational training certificate while 52.2% held a university degree or higher.

Working Experience of Respondents

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Less than 1 year	4	4.3
	1-5 years	44	47.8
	6-10 years	35	38.0
	Above 10 years	9	9.8
	Total	92	100.0

Source: Primary data, (2025)

The respondents' employment experience is shown in above. The working experience of the responders piqued the researcher's curiosity. 4.3% of the 92 respondents had less than a year's work experience, 47.8% had one to five years, 38.0% had six to ten years, and 9.8% had more than ten years.

Presentation of Findings

The results of the data analysis are shown in this part; the study was to examine the contribution of broadcast media campaign in law enforcement on crime prevention in Rwanda at Rwanda broadcasting agency.

Contribution of broadcast media campaigns in law enforcement and crime prevention

Statement	S D		D		Not Sure		A		S A		Total		
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	N	Mean	Sd
Broadcast media used to provide general information to the public on how to avoid victimization	0	0	0	0	0	0	44	47.8	48	52.2	92	4.52	.502
TV & Radio used to broadcast the crime prevention messages in reducing crime in community	7	7.6	29	31.5	0	0	56	60.9	0	0	92	3.14	1.105
Broadcast media campaigns reduce the crime in community	0	0	0	0	0	0	66	71.7	26	28.3	92	4.28	.453
Crime prevention messages through broadcast media change the community behavior	0	0	0	0	13	14.1	51	55.4	28	30.4	92	4.16	.651
Media campaigns are in encouraging the community to report crimes to law enforcement	0	0	0	0	0	0	33	35.9	59	64.1	92	4.64	.482
Overall Mean												4.148	

Source: Primary data, (2025)

The findings are presented in above table to describe the contribution of broadcast media campaigns in law enforcement on crime prevention in Rwanda at Rwanda broadcasting agency (RBA). Out of 92 respondents, 47.8% agreed and 52.2% strongly agreed that broadcast media used to give general advice to the public on how to avoid victimization, according to the data analysis. On that the TV & Radio used to broadcast the crime prevention messages in reducing crime in community, the 7.6% strongly disagreed, 31.5% disagreed, and 60.9% agreed. To the media campaigns reduce the crime in community, the 71.7% agreed and 28.3% strongly agreed.

Of those surveyed, 14.1% were unsure, 55.4% agreed, and 30.4% strongly agreed that crime prevention messages conveyed through broadcast media alter community behavior. Of those surveyed, 35.9% agreed and 64.1% strongly agreed that media efforts are helping to encourage the public to report crimes to law enforcement organizations. With an aggregate mean score of 4.148, which fell between agree (4) and strongly agree (5), it was clear that law enforcement's use of broadcast media campaigns significantly reduces crime in Rwanda.

Additionally, nineteen law enforcement officials from the media department and the crime prevention division participated in a focus group discussion responses included; to the public engagement and crime prevention on how public respond to the crime prevention campaigns aired on broadcast media, law enforcement officers agreed that public's response to crime prevention campaigns aired on broadcast media can vary widely depending on several factors, such as the campaign's content, the medium used (TV or radio), and the demographics of the target audience.

Law enforcement officers agreed that the public's response to crime prevention campaigns is shaped by how well the message resonates with their specific concerns, the credibility of the source, and how actionable the advice is. Campaigns that feel relevant, practical, and sensitive to the audience's needs are more likely to have a positive impact, leading to greater awareness, behavioral change, and community involvement (Marsh & Melville, 2019). Law enforcement officers responded that the public's willingness to cooperate with law enforcement after hearing or watching crime-related campaigns can vary, but it showed that well-designed crime prevention campaigns positively influence public attitudes and encourage cooperation.

To the feedback mechanisms, on the systems that are in place for the public to provide feedback on crime prevention campaigns broadcast in the media, law enforcement officers agreed that local authorities and law enforcement agencies may host community meetings or town halls to directly engage with residents. These gatherings allow people to share their thoughts on crime prevention efforts, discuss their concerns, and suggest improvements. Social media is frequently used by campaigns to interact with the public directly. People can comment, share their opinions, or participate in discussions. Social

media platforms (like Twitter, Facebook, or Instagram) allow for real-time feedback, with hashtags often used to track engagement and sentiment (Morgan & Signorielli, 2017).

Crime Prevention

Researcher analyzed the dependent variables of crime prevention in Rwanda at Rwanda broadcasting agency (RBA).

Crime Prevention

Statement	S D		D		Not Sure		A		S A		Total		
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	N	Mean	Sd
Broadcast media develop the Level of community engagement in crime prevention activities	0	0	19	20.7	6	6.5	67	72.8	0	0	92	3.52	.818
Broadcast media facilitate the public awareness of crime prevention strategies	0	0	0	0	0	0	61	66.3	31	33.7	92	4.34	.475
Broadcast media promotes the public willingness to cooperate with law enforcement in crime prevention	0	0	0	0	0	0	39	42.4	53	57.6	92	4.58	.497
Broadcast media play a vital role in disseminating information on crime trends	0	0	0	0	0	0	67	72.8	25	27.2	92	4.27	.447
Broadcast media influence people's understanding of the criminal justice system	8	8.7	13	14.1	0	0	71	77.2	0	0	92	3.46	1.032
Overall Mean												4.034	

Source: Primary data, (2025)

The results of dependent variables for crime prevention in the Rwanda Broadcasting Agency (RBA) are shown in above table. Out of 92 respondents, 72.8% agreed that broadcast media raises the level of community involvement in crime prevention initiatives, while 20.7% disagreed and 6.5% were unsure, according to the data analysis. On that broadcast media facilitates the public awareness of crime prevention strategies, the 66.3% agreed and 33.7% strongly agreed. To the broadcast media promotes the public willingness to cooperate with law enforcement in crime prevention, the 42.4% agreed and 57.6% strongly agreed.

Of those surveyed, 72.8% agreed and 27.2% strongly agreed that the mass media is essential for spreading information about crime trends. Regarding the idea that broadcast media affects how people perceive the criminal justice system, 77.2% of respondents agreed, 14.1% disagreed, and 8.7 severely disagreed. The overall mean score of 4.034, which fell between agree (4) and highly agree (5), it showed that there was significant crime prevention in Rwanda at Rwanda broadcasting agency (RBA).

Relationship between broadcast media campaign in law enforcement and crime prevention

	Contribution of broadcast media Crime prevention campaigns in law enforcement		
Contribution of broadcast media campaigns in law enforcement	Pearson Correlation	1	.868**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	92	92
Crime prevention	Pearson Correlation	.868**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	92	92

Source: Primary data, (2025)

Above table presents the relationship between the broadcast media campaign in law enforcement and crime prevention in Rwanda at Rwanda broadcasting agency. Version 26.0 of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program was used to calculate the Pearson coefficients. The data analysis resulted that the relationship between contribution of broadcast media campaigns in law enforcement and crime prevention was .868**. The results demonstrated a statistically significant correlation between the broadcast media campaign in law enforcement and crime prevention in Rwanda at Rwanda broadcasting agency.

IV. DISCUSSIONS

Davis et al. (2016) evaluated the impact of anti-drug media campaigns in urban settings. Their findings indicated that such campaigns, which included a mix of television advertisement, social media posts, and community outreach programs, led to increased public awareness about the risks of drug use and a subsequent decrease in drug-related crimes. This study indicated that the 55.4% agreed that crime prevention messages through broadcast media change the community behavior. The 60.9% agreed that the TV & Radio used to broadcast the crime prevention messages in reducing crime in community.

The connection between media consumption and public attitudes toward crime and justice, the study revealed that frequent exposure to televised crime reports with strong audio-visual elements (such as crime scene footage or interviews with law enforcement) tends to cultivate heightened awareness of criminal issues, which can either increase fear of crime or motivate citizens to cooperate with police in prevention efforts (Dowler, 2016). The current study presented that the 67.4% strongly agreed that Media campaigns are in encouraging the community to prevent crimes in societies. The 22.8% agreed and 77.2% strongly agreed that the collaboration between law enforcement and media helps reduce crime.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study examined the contribution of broadcast media campaigns in law enforcement and crime prevention in Rwanda at Rwanda broadcasting agency. Based on the findings of the data analysis, conclusions were drawn. The study concluded that the broadcast media campaigns in law enforcement has the significant contribution on crime prevention, and there was a significant correlation between the effort of broadcast media campaigns in law enforcement and crime prevention in Rwanda.

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